

H. pylori a Neurological Disease? A Case Report with Literature Review

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Introduction

An infection with *H. Pylori* induces chronic inflammation of the underlying mucosa. The disease can be contracted in the first few years of life and would remain active unless it is actively treated. Its frequency increases with older age, institutionalization, and lower socioeconomic status, indirectly associated with hygienic practices.

The gut-brain axis is a complex bidirectional communication network involving the central nervous system (CNS), peripheral nervous system (PNS) including the enteric nervous system (ENS), and the autonomic nervous system (ANS). This network modulates gastrointestinal (GI) function by regulating the GI immune system, mucosal inflammation, and the composition of the gut microbiota. These regulatory processes are influenced by stress, emotions, and environmental factors. The gut-brain axis plays a crucial role in maintaining homeostasis in both the upper (e.g., peptic ulcer, functional dyspepsia) and lower (e.g., irritable bowel syndrome, inflammatory bowel disease) GI tract.

Case Report

A 29-year-old male presents to the emergency department with intermittent, recurrent, sharp, localized left epigastric pain, without weight loss or evidence of gastrointestinal bleeding. He denies previous use of aspirin or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. He reports episodes of bloating and intermittent diarrhea/ small caliber feces.

On abdominal examination, tympanism is evidence by auscultation and percussion, left epigastric tenderness is revealed at palpation. A serologic test for *Helicobacter pylori* is performed, and the results are positive. Asterix and tremors, positive. Imaging Tests are negative for perforation or structural abnormalities. He then receives a 10-day course of triple therapy (omeprazole, amoxicillin, and clarithromycin). Six weeks later, the patient returns with the same symptoms.

Based on the patient's symptoms, serological tests for *H. pylori* were ordered, which showed a positive result.

H. pylori and the Nervous System

H. pylori and Cognitive Function:

•Verbal Memory and Dementia: Studies have shown a correlation between *H. pylori* seropositivity and poorer performance on verbal memory tests, suggesting a link to cognitive decline. This association may be related to the ammonia production by *H. pylori*, similar to urease-positive bacteria known to cause hepatic encephalopathy. Further research suggests *H. pylori* infection as a potential risk factor for dementia development, possibly through heightened neurodegenerative processes.

•Early Cognitive Development: *H. pylori* infection might also negatively impact early stages of cognitive development, although more studies are needed to confirm this.

•Brain-Gut Axis: *H. pylori* may influence brain-gut axis function and visceral sensitivity. This could occur through the release of neurotransmitters and hormones, activation of inflammatory pathways, or alterations in digestive tract motility. These processes could potentially lead to visceral hyperalgesia (increased pain perception) and atypical chest pain. Additionally, increased autonomic nervous system (ANS) activity has been observed in *H. pylori*-positive individuals.

•Digestive Motility: *H. pylori*'s influence on digestive tract motility might be due to its direct local effect or indirectly through the aforementioned ANS and hormonal pathways. Studies have investigated the impact of *H. pylori* infection on esophageal peristalsis (contractions) and their amplitude and duration.

•Neurological Effects: The influence of *H. pylori* on the brain-gut axis could stem from a direct neurotoxic effect, triggering inflammation in nerves, or microelement deficiencies.

•Parkinson's Disease: Research suggests a possible link between *H. pylori* infection and an increased risk of developing Parkinson's disease. Conversely, eradication of *H. pylori* may lead to improvements in motor symptoms associated with Parkinson's.

•Alzheimer's Disease: *H. pylori* infection has been associated with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), often considered a precursor to Alzheimer's disease, and potentially with Alzheimer's disease itself.

Fig.1 Changes at the microbiome-gut-brain axis during *Helicobacter pylori* and Non-*H. pylori Helicobacter* (NHPH) infection © 2021 Gorlé, Bauwens, Haesebrouck, Smet and Vandenbroucke

Fig.2 Illustration of *H. pylori* structure. Adapted by Joe Bolanos

Antimicrobial Resistance

- Drug efflux pumps.
- Cure rates have dropped dramatically
- For most bacterial infectious diseases appropriate therapy is devised on the basis of antibiotic susceptibility testing, and the expectation is that more than 95% of infections.

Fig.3 The inflammatory response in *Helicobacter pylori* infection. ©2014 Baishideng Publishing Group Inc. CC BY-NC 4.0

Discussion

At the first visit, the patient was treated with the first-line treatment of Omeprazole, Clarithromycin, and Amoxicillin, which is the standard treatment for *H. pylori* infection. However, after six weeks, his symptoms persisted, for which the patient consulted again, this time receiving a second-line regimen of pharmaceuticals, which is used if resistance is suspected: Metronidazole, Amoxicillin, and Omeprazole or quadruple therapy.

After completion of treatment, symptoms waned and ceased.

Standard initial treatment (use one of the following three options)

Triple therapy for 7–14 days
PPI, healing dose twice/day* Amoxicillin, 1 g twice/day† Clarithromycin, 500 mg twice/day

Second-line therapy, if triple therapy involving clarithromycin was used initially (use one or the other)

Triple therapy for 7–14 days
PPI, healing dose once/day*
Amoxicillin, 1 g twice/day
Metronidazole, 500 mg (or 400 mg) twice/day§

H. pylori is a known carcinogenic microorganism that, if left untreated, can cause MALT lymphomas.

Current evidence suggests a correlative link between *H. pylori* infection and cognitive decline, dementia, Parkinson's, and other neurological presentations. Many neurodegenerative diseases likely arise from a complex interplay of factors. However, chronic systemic inflammation and the development of autoantibodies are increasingly recognized as mechanisms that contribute to the initiation, progression, and ultimate clinical outcomes of these disorders.

However, to definitively establish causality, future research should focus on elucidating the underlying mechanisms.

This may involve investigating the potential role of neuroinflammation, neurotransmitter modulation, or direct neurotoxic effects of *H. pylori* or its metabolites. Additionally, longitudinal studies with larger cohorts are needed to strengthen the current associations.

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Probiotics reduce the adverse effects, prevent complications and improve the outcome of *H. pylori*-eradication therapy.

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